

A Study of the Effect of Dry Oxygen on Alkylthio- and Alkoxyantimonite

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Manuscript received 31 August 1976, revised 25 January 1977, accepted 27 April 1977

Soluble and volatile alkylthioantimonite $Sb(SR)_3$ has been found to undergo decomposition in contact with dry oxygen to yield volatile dithiol RSSR alongwith an insoluble and non-volatile mixture of Sb_2O_3 and $(RS)_2SbO$ in the ratio 3.5 : 1, as the final products of decomposition, whereas antimony trialkoxide $Sb(OR)_3$ remain inactive towards dry oxygen. An endeavour has been made to focus on the mode of decomposition of the alkylthio derivatives with respect to the inertness of alkoxyantimonites towards dry oxygen. The decomposition of the alkylthio antimonites proceeds probably through the following two plausible steps involving SR free radical alongwith the formation of dithiol RSSR :

IN comparison to metal-oxygen-carbon bonded metal aloxides¹⁻⁴ $M(OR)_n$, alkylthio derivatives⁵⁻⁷ $M(SR)_n$, having metal-sulphur-carbon bonds, are comparatively of recent interest. While carrying out the isolation and studies of number of alkylthioantimonites^{7,8} an interesting behaviour was observed on storage of these alkylthio derivatives $Sb(SR)_3$ ^{7,8}. White solids were found to separate out slowly from these colourless and volatile alkylthioantimonites^{7,8}, even when they were kept in a stoppered flask. In contrast to the soluble and volatile nature of these alkylthio derivatives^{7,8} these separated solid masses were found to be non-volatile and insoluble in the inert organic solvents like benzene but tend to redissolve in the medium of parent thiol on heating. Further experiments showed that the rate of decomposition of the liquid thioantimonites appear to become almost negligible under vacuum or in an atmosphere of nitrogen. From this, it appears that the atmospheric oxygen played a role in these decompositions occurring during storage and hence the reaction of alkylthioantimonite^{7,8} with dry oxygen was investigated.

To establish a comparative survey of Sb-S-C bonded thiol derivatives^{7,8} with aloxides possessing Sb-O-C bonds towards the effect of dry oxygen, the similar study has also been extended⁹⁻¹¹ to antimony tri-ethoxide $Sb(OEt)_3$.

Results and Discussions

An exothermic reaction was observed alongwith the gradual separation of insoluble solid, when dry oxygen was passed under rigorous moisturefree condition into a benzene solution containing butylthioantimonite^{7,8} and the dry oxygen was passed for

about 10 hours. After filtration and drying, the separated insoluble solid was found on analysis to be a probable mixture of Sb_2O_3 and $(BuS)_2SbO$ in the ratio of 3.5 : 1. The filtrate gave of $BuSSBu$ on distillation. Further passage of dry oxygen through a suspension of the insoluble solid in benzene did not produce any noticeable analytical change. The results have been summarised in the flow sheet No. 1.

When a benzene solution containing ethoxyantimonite^{7,9-11} $Sb(OEt)_3$ was treated with dry oxygen under exactly similar condition any physical or chemical change did not take place. (Vide flow sheet No. 2).

Thus, it was observed that butylthioantimonite^{7,8} was found to be sensitive even to dry oxygen to yield oxide and dibutylsulphide $BuSSBu$, whereas the antimony triethoxide^{7,8,10,11} has been found to be quite stable towards dry oxygen. The more easily oxidisable nature of thiols and alkylthio groups, with respect to alcohols or alkoxy groups may be the probable cause of the reactivity of alkylthioantimonites^{7,8} in comparison to alkoxyantimonites,^{7,9-11} towards dry oxygen.

Thiols and alcohols behave quite differently towards oxidising agents. Oxidation of alcohols proceeds, in general, with an increase in the oxidation level of carbon rather than that of oxygen.

hence there is formation of carbonyl groups, but not peroxides :

This is due to the fact that O—H (111 Kcal) in alcohol is strong bond and needs a powerful oxidising agent to achieve one-electron oxidation of oxygen by removing a hydrogen atom from the hydroxyl group of an alcohol :

Apart from it, the hydrogen oxygen of an alcohol is not found to accept an oxygen atom from mild oxidising agents like hydrogen peroxide :

In the oxidation of thiols,

- (i) Sulphur is more easily oxidised than carbon.
- (ii) the compounds in which sulphur is in higher oxidation state, are found to be quite stable.
- (iii) as the strength of S—H bonds (83 Kcal) is considerably less than that of O—H bonds (111 Kcal), the reaction mechanisms, which are unfavourable for alcohols, are found to be quite favourable for thiols.

Thus, it is observed that the oxidation of thiols, with a mild oxidising agents like atmospheric oxygen produce dialkyldisulphide RSSR probably with the formation of alkylthio radicals :

Hence the decomposition of the alkylthioantimonites⁷⁸ proceeds probably through the following two plausible steps by a mechanism^{78,18} involving SR free radical alongwith the formation of dithiol RSSR :

As a matter of fact, the, presence of (BuS)₃SbO, Sb₂O₃ and BuSSBu have been detected in the decomposed product. Probably due to the insoluble nature of both (BuS)₃SbO and Sb₂O₃ in the medium of dry benzene, the second step of the reaction does not proceed to completion.

Experimental

Butylthioantimonite⁷⁸ was prepared by the reaction of anhydrous antimony trichloride with butane-thiol in presence of gaseous ammonia⁷⁸. Ethoxyantimonite⁷⁹⁻¹¹ was prepared by the reaction of anhydrous antimony trichloride with sodium ethoxide in the molar ratio 1 : 3 as described⁷⁹⁻¹¹. Both of these derivatives have been isolated under rigorous moisturefree condition⁷ and were purified before use by distillation under vacuo⁷. [B.pt.s, Sb(OEt)₃ 94.5/10.0, and Sb(SBu)₃ 160/0.3 respectively].

The trivalent antimony present in the butylthioantimonite⁷⁸ was estimated by standard potassium bromate solution after decomposing the thioderivative⁷⁸ with bromine in the hydrochloric acid medium as described^{78,18}. In ethoxyantimonite^{7, 9-11} antimony(III) was determined by the similar method^{78,13} after dissolving the compound in the medium of hot hydrochloric acid. In the insoluble residue obtained after the decomposition of alkylthio derivative, ⁷⁸ the total metal content [i.e. antimony(III)+antimony(V)] was found out by the above mentioned method^{78,13} after digesting the residue with bromine in the medium of hot hydrochloric acid, and trivalent antimony was estimated by direct titration with standard potassium bromate¹³ after digesting the solid in the medium of hot hydrochloric acid. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically¹⁴ as BaSO₄.

An exothermic reaction was observed alongwith the gradual separation of insoluble solid, when dry oxygen was passed under rigorous moisturefree condition into a benzene (70 g) solution containing⁷⁸ 6.34 g of Sb(SBu)₃ [Analysis: Found : Sb, 31.1, S, 24.0 ; Calcd. for Sb(SBu)₃, Sb 31.3, S, 24.7%] and the dry oxygen was passed for about 10 hours. The separated residue was filtered and dried under vacuo to give a non-volatile and insoluble product (2.69 g) and was subjected to analysis. [Found : Sb^{III+V}, 69.1, Sb^{III} 60.4, S, 5.45. A mixture of Sb₂O₃ and (BuS)₃SbO in the ratio 3.5 : 1 requires Sb^{III+V} 68.05, Sb^{III} 59.8, S, 6.75%] Dry Oxygen was further passed for about 40 hrs. through a suspension of 0.91 g of this insoluble residue in the medium of dry benzene under a rigorous moisturefree condition. 0.87 g of the insoluble product was recovered and was analysed. (Found : Sb^{III+V} 68.5 ; Sb^{III} 60.0, S, 5.2%).

The filtrate gave a 3.9 g of a colourless liquid b.pt. 117-118° on distillation at 20 mm Hg. and was analysed (Found : C, 52.9, H, 10.1, S, 35.2, Calcd. for BuSSBu ; C, 53.9, H 10.2, S, 35.9%). The results have been summarised in flow sheet No. 1.

No physical or chemical change was observed when

dry oxygen was passed through a benzene solution (60g) containing 4.67 g of Sb(OEt)₃ [Analysis, Sb 47.6, Calcd. for Sb(OEt)₃ ; Sb, 47.3%], and 4.35 g of liquid was recovered and was analysed Found : Sb, 47.9%, Calcd for Sb(CEt)₃ : Sb, 47.3% (Vide Flow Sheet no. 2).

Flow Sheet No. 1

Effect of Dry Oxygen on Sb(SBu)₃

Flow Sheet No. 2

Effect of Dry Oxygen on Sb(OEt)₃

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